

LEADERSHIP CHALLENGES OF THE FOURTH INDUSTRIAL REVOLUTION DURING THE PANDEMIC-INDUCED VUCA ENVIRONMENT: LITERATURE REVIEW

¹Tursunkulov I., ²Aktamov Sh.

¹Business Faculty, University of Digital Economics and Agrotechnologies, Uzbekistan

²Dr., Business Faculty, University of Digital Economics and Agrotechnologies, Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *The Pandemic has accelerated society's digital development toward the Fourth Industrial Revolution, which presented significant obstacles to managers. The impact of digital disruption must be managed alongside the more volatile, unpredictable, complex, and ambiguous conditions called "VUCA" to We have analysed 15 scientific papers from the "Web of Science" and "Scopus" databases from 2020 to 2022 and identified four leadership challenges for Industry 4.0: Leadership style, Mismatch of skills, Capabilities of leaders to transition and Working environment. Leadership style is more important to manage in an Industrial Revolution environment than technical skills. Moreover, the incapability of leaders of digital adaptation, embracing Industry 4.0, directing the changes during the transition, and relying upon only technical skills can be challenging for future leaders.*

Keywords: *leadership, digital adaptation, skills, industry 4.0., industry readiness.*

JEL classification: D90, M10, M50.

1. Introduction.

The term VUCA, or "volatility, uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity", was coined by the United States Army to describe the adverse conditions and geopolitical environment created by the end of the Cold War (Nangia & Mohsin, 2020). Company executives, management, and some academics have adopted it to describe in one word the problematic situations caused by external factors, which is now in use as a phrase to explain the pandemic and rapid development of technology-caused situations. Companies and firms are experiencing high uncertainty in the global and domestic markets due to the COVID-19 Pandemic-induced VUCA environment. Because of the lockdown in China and the Russian-Ukraine conflict resulted in supply-chain disruptions, shortages and high input costs. Additionally, the global increase in inflation is leading to monetary tightening, raising the cost of funding for businesses. Scholars have argued that economic downturns can sufficiently reduce companies' liquidity (Martos-Vila & Shi, 2022).

On the other hand, the COVID-19 pandemic has changed people's lives and work environments. People worldwide have been forced to stay home, relying on digital technologies to continue their lives and work as best they can. COVID-19 has thus accelerated society's digital transformation toward Industry 4.0. Moreover, this situation has presented many challenges to managers. Therefore, this literature review aims to identify the leadership challenges of The Fourth Industrial Revolution during the VUCA environment.

The Fourth Industrial Revolution. The Fourth Industrial Revolution is a type of disruptive change in technology that encompasses multiple change drivers (Frey & Osborne, 2013). This transformation includes work, consumer ethics, the Internet of Things, robotics, cloud computing,

and many other areas. It generally entails widespread digitalisation and technological advancement across various industries and sectors. Industry 4.0 contributed to the Fourth Industrial Revolution by utilising the disruptive technologies discussed in the preceding section. Such applications might include implementing robotics or automation in a factory's assembly line. The critical distinction between Industry 4.0 and current technology is the emphasis on automation rather than manual labour for specific tasks (Taylor, 2005).

Leadership during the Fourth Industrial Revolution. The impact of digital disruption must be managed alongside the more volatile, unpredictable, complex, and ambiguous conditions referred to as "VUCA" in recent years (Bawany, 2017). Leaders face the challenge of reestablishing trust and respect in leadership and business. They are expected to lead companies through times of turbulence and uncertainty, to show the way forward, and to set a good example. Furthermore, this is occurring in an increasingly disruptive global economy, a climate of cynicism and mistrust - challenging economic and political conditions.

Leadership in the digital age is all about the ability to impact and influence followers and stakeholders towards achieving the organisation's mission and objectives by effectively demonstrating the suite of next-generation leadership competencies, such as cognitive readiness skills, critical thinking, and emotional and social intelligence competencies such as empathy and relationship management (Bawany, 2017).

The fourth industrial revolution represents the combination of cyber-physical systems, the Internet of Things, and the Internet of Systems. In this fourth revolution, new technologies will evolve to combine the physical, digital, and biological worlds. As Schwab (2016) argues, public-private research collaborations should increase and be structured towards building knowledge and human capital for all to thrive in this environment. There will be enormous managerial leadership challenges as the impact of technology and the disruption will result in an exogenous force over which leaders would sometimes have little or no control. However, it is the role of leaders to guide their teams and to be mindful of these forces when making business decisions that would impact the sustainability of their organisations.

VUCA. The expression VUCA, which stands for volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity, is now widely used. In a VUCA world, the essential drivers of organisational performance – like strategic planning – are ineffective, and efforts to understand the future become helpless (Bennett & Lemoine, 2014).

In stable environments, organisations traditionally trust experience, routines, learning, and scale; however, new situations require companies to find new solutions to the volatility problem (Bennett & Lemoine, 2014). At the same time, to understand an uncertain environment, managers should actively explore cause and effect factors (Bartsch, 2015), gather more information, and develop knowledge affecting the uncertain situation (Bennett & Lemoine, 2014).

A complex situation is characterised by many interconnected parts and requires a great effort to collect, digest, and understand the critical data (Bennett & Lemoine, 2014). The information concerning the nature of complexity is available or possible to predict. However, the sheer volume and nature of the problem can be overwhelming (Raghuramapatruni & Kosuri, 2017). Ambiguity in VUCA describes circumstances where there is doubt about the nature of cause-and-effect relationships (Bennett & Lemoine, 2014). For instance, Nangia and Mohsin (2020) found that the number of cultures, populations, genders and changing demographic patterns of consumers based on geography causes ambiguity in the Indian IT industry.

2. Methodology.

The five-step systematic review method was used for this literature review. The procedure is as follows:

- Step 1: Framing questions for a review.
- Step 2: Identifying relevant work.
- Step 3: Assessing the quality of studies
- Step 4: Summarising the evidence.
- Step 5: Interpreting the findings.

2.1. Framing review question. The transformation process to Industry 4.0 situations depends on leadership adapting to the Industry 4.0 era. Managers must be qualified and promoted to meet and be prepared for such difficulties to successfully transition to Industry 4.0 Leadership (Puhovichová & Jankelová, 2021). Thus, this literature review is being conducted to identify the Fourth Industrial Revolution's leadership challenges. According to the trend in research on the topic "Industrial Revolution 4.0" increased when the COVID-19 Pandemic began in 2020.

Moreover, this one more time proves that the Pandemic has accelerated digital transformation toward Industry 4.0. Thus, this literature review aims to answer the open-ended question, "How to be a Leader in the Fourth Industrial Revolution?"

2.2. Identifying relevant work. The articles in this review were chosen from the "Web of Science" and "Scopus" databases. The literature search was

also restricted to publications from 2020 to 2022 to increase relevance with the Pandemic-induced VUCA environment. The articles were selected based on "Industrial Revolution 4.0" keywords followed by "Leadership". Figure 2 illustrates the keywords and criteria used for selecting relevant articles from the databases chosen in the literature review.

Figure 2. Summary of Search Results.

Keywords and criteria	"Industrial Revolution 4.0"	"Leadership"	Limit to 2020-2022	Limit to articles (and exclude review articles)	Selected papers
Databases					
Web of Science	1340	28	22	15	15
Scopus	919	32	20	8	8
Duplicated Papers				8	8
Total papers to review				15	15

2.3. Selection of the studies. Articles were selected based on the review question from the search results based on keywords. The selected articles must have a central theme based on the Fourth Industrial Revolution. In addition, articles must discuss Leadership challenges or mention

leadership skills regarding the Fourth Industrial Revolution. Based on this principle, 15 articles were selected from the "Web of Science" database.

Figure 3. List of selected papers.

#	Authors	Publication Year	Journal
1	Balog, K	2020	Strategic management
2	Kiraz et al.	2020	Journal of the faculty of engineering and architecture of Gazi University
3	Marnewick et al.	2020	IEEE Access
4	Satpathy et al.	2020	Rupkatha journal on interdisciplinary studies in humanities
5	Hermawan et al.	2020	Journal of Asian Finance Economics and business
6	Subramaniam et al.	2021	International Journal of Online and biomedical engineering
7	Rusly et al.	2021	Polish Journal of Management studies
8	Amin et al.	2021	Zbornik radova ekonomskog fakulteta u rijeci-proceedings of rijeka faculty of economics
9	Aminah. S & Saksono. H	2021	Jurnal komunikasi-malaysian journal of communication
10	Soomro et al.	2021	Informatics-BASEL
11	Wilson et al.	2021	Education and information technologies
12	da Silva et al.	2021	Revista tecnologia e sociedade
13	Jayashree et al.	2022	Sustainable production and consumption
14	Coopasamy. S & Botha. A	2022	South African Journal of Industrial engineering
15	Long et al.	2022	International Journal of Technology

3. Summary of the evidence.

Based on the papers, we have analysed the research methodology used in papers, leadership challenges and possible ways to overcome these challenges. Regarding the methodology, we have developed two groups: in Group 1, the authors used quantitative methodology, and in Group 2, the authors used qualitative methodology.

Furthermore, regarding the data collection, two groups were divided between primary and secondary data collection methods. Finally, regarding leadership challenges and solutions, we clustered findings into groups according to their characteristics.

Nine studies out of fifteen employed quantitative analyses to examine the leadership challenges of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. Moreover, most authors (12 papers) collected data for their studies through surveys and interviews, while only three studies used secondary data for the analysis.

Figure 4. Research methodologies used in selected papers.

Group	Methodology	Number of papers	Authors
1	Quantitative methodology	9	Balog, K (2020); Kiraz et al. (2020); Marnewick et al. (2020); Hermawan et al. (2020); Amin et al. (2021); Soomro et al. (2021); Wilson et al. (2021); Jayashree et al. (2022); Long et al. (2022)
2	Qualitative methodology	6	Satpathy et al. (2020); Subramaniam et al. (2021); Rusly et al. (2021); Aminah. S & Saksono. H (2021); da Silva et al. (2021); Coopasamy. S & Botha. A (2022)
Total papers		15	

Figure 5. Data collection methods used in selected papers.

Group	Methodology	Number of papers	Authors
1	Primary data (Survey, interview)	12	Balog, K (2020); Marnewick et al. (2020); Hermawan et al. (2020); Amin et al. (2021); Soomro et al. (2021); Wilson et al. (2021); Long et al. (2022); Satpathy et al. (2020); Subramaniam et al. (2021); Rusly et al. (2021); da Silva et al. (2021); Coopasamy. S & Botha. A (2022)
2	Secondary data	3	Kiraz et al. (2020); Aminah. S & Saksono. H (2021); Jayashree et al. (2022)
Total papers		15	

Figure 6. Leadership challenges of Industry 4.0.

Group	Leadership challenges	Number of papers	Authors
1	Leadership style: Traditional ways of leadership are not effective in future	8	Balog, K (2020); Marnewick et al. (2020); Amin et al. (2021); Aminah. S & Saksono. H (2021); da Silva et al. (2021); Jayashree et al. (2022); Coopasamy. S & Botha. A (2022); Long et al. (2022);
2	The mismatch of skills: Technical skills are not enough for future industry readiness	2	Satpathy et al. (2020); Subramaniam et al. (2021);

3	Leadership capabilities: The capability of directing the changes, Digital adaptation, embracing Industry 4.0, and successfully transitioning to Industry 4.0.	4	Kiraz et al. (2020); Rusly et al. (2021); Soomro et al. (2021); Wilson et al. (2021);
4	Work environment: To create an environment that can motivate employees and improve the quality of HR and performance.	1	Hermawan et al. (2020);
Total papers		15	

According to the literature, we have identified leadership challenges and clustered them into four groups based on their characteristics. Most authors found that changing leadership style was more important to manage in the fourth Industrial Revolution environment. At the same time, four authors believe leaders must be capable of digital adaptation, embracing Industry 4.0 and directing the changes during the transition. In contrast, other authors believe that for future leaders, only technical skills are not enough; finally, they must motivate employees and improve the quality of human resources if they want a successful transition to Industry 4.0.

Figure 6. Leadership challenges of Industry 4.0.

Group	Leadership challenges	Possible solutions	Authors
1	Leadership style: Traditional ways of leadership are not effective in future	The agile way of leadership, like the “servant-leadership” style, is the most appropriate for the future; it makes leaders efficient and motivated.	Balog, K (2020); Marnewick et al. (2020);
		Future leaders must move away from authoritarian, bureaucratic, and task-orientated leadership styles and embrace transformational, people-orientated, and charismatic leadership styles.	Coopasamy. S & Botha. A (2022);
		Future leaders should encourage innovative concepts and concentrate on making the organisation more proficient than their competitors. Adaptability, solving complex problems, and flexibility are seen as relevant.	Amin et al. (2021); da Silva et al. (2021); Jayashree et al. (2022);

		Blockchain Leadership is the appropriate model for achieving success for organisations in the era of IR 4.0. It is a digital, transparent, ethical leadership capability that is sustainable for the future.	Aminah & Saksono (2021); Long et al. (2022);
2	The mismatch of skills: Technical skills are not enough for future industry readiness	Future leaders should equip themselves with various soft skills like English language development, communication, personality development, critical thinking, problem-solving, entrepreneurial and team-building skills	Satpathy et al. (2020); Subramaniam et al. (2021);
3	Leadership capabilities: The capability of directing the changes, Digital adaptation, embracing Industry 4.0, and successfully transitioning to Industry 4.0.	To be capable of thinking strategically. To create a digital transformation roadmap before making significant investments.	Kiraz et al. (2020);
		Four dimensions of internal forces driving digital adaptation are business strategy, value creation, digital leadership and digital talent.	Rusly et al. (2021);
		Older organisations have a better approach in terms of leadership to embracing Industry 4.0: Leadership skills and capabilities are developed faster and better in old and large organisations.	Soomro et al. (2021);
4	Work environment: To create an environment that can motivate employees and improve the quality of HR and performance.	Productive employment depends largely on proficient leadership, stimulating employees' readiness through knowledge enhancement.	Wilson et al. (2021);
		To implement Employee Engagement, leaders must focus on several aspects, such as Team Work, Pleasant Working Conditions, Growth Opportunities, Flexible Working Practices, Good Leadership, and Management	Hermawan et al. (2020);

Practices because Employee
Engagement
significantly affects Employee
Performance.

Total papers

15

4. Discussion.

Most studies employed quantitative analyses via surveys and interviews to examine future leadership challenges. From the methodological part of the studies, we can conclude that primary data is more important to understanding leadership issues.

According to the literature, we have identified leadership challenges and clustered them into four groups based on their characteristics. The first group is Leadership style. Traditional leadership styles are ineffective in IR 4.0, as leaders must embrace transformational, people-orientated, charismatic leadership styles. Future leaders should encourage innovative concepts and concentrate on making the organisation more proficient than their competitors. Finally, Digital, transparent, ethical leadership capability is sustainable for the future (Balog, K., 2020; Marnewick et al., 2020; Amin et al., 2021; Aminah. S & Saksono. H., 2021; da Silva et al., 2021; Jayashree et al., 2022; Coopasamy. S & Botha.A., 2022; Long et al., 2022).

The second group is the mismatch of skills. Relying upon only technical skills is not enough for future leaders. Developing soft skills such as English language development, communication, personality development, critical thinking, problem-solving, entrepreneurship, and team building are essential for success in a fast-paced and technologically advanced world (Satpathy et al., 2020; Subramaniam et al., 2021).

The next group is the Capabilities of leaders to transition. Leaders must be able to think strategically and create a digital transformation roadmap before making significant investments in IR 4.0. environment. The four internal forces driving digital adaptation are business strategy, value creation, digital leadership, and digital talent. In this case, older organisations have a better method in terms of leadership to embracing Industry 4.0 and skills and capabilities are developed faster and better in old and large organisations (Kiraz et al., 2020; Rusly et al., 2021; Soomro et al., 2021; Wilson et al., 2021).

Finally, the last group is the Working environment. Leaders must implement Employee Engagement practices and focus on aspects such as Teamwork, Pleasant Working Conditions, Growth Opportunities, Flexible Working Practices, Good Leadership, and Management Practices. Creating an environment that can motivate employees and improve the quality of human resources and performance is essential (Hermawan et al., 2020).

In a nutshell, leadership style and soft skills are more critical to managing in an Industrial Revolution environment than traditional leadership style and technical skills. Authors believe the incapability of leaders of digital adaptation, embracing Industry 4.0, directing the changes during the transition, and relying upon only technical skills can be challenging for future leaders.

5. Conclusion.

The Pandemic has accelerated society's digital development toward the Fourth Industrial Revolution, which presented significant obstacles to managers. The impact of digital disruption must be managed alongside the more volatile, unpredictable, complex, and ambiguous conditions called "VUCA" in recent years (Bawany, 2016). Leaders face the difficulty of reestablishing trust

and respect in leadership and business. They are expected to guide firms through times of turmoil and uncertainty, to indicate the way forward, and to set a good example. Leadership in the digital age is all about the ability to impact and influence followers and stakeholders towards achieving the organisation's mission and objectives. Accordingly, this literature review attempted to identify the Fourth Industrial Revolution's leadership issues in the VUCA environment and answer the open-ended question, "How to be a Leader in the Fourth Industrial Revolution?"

According to the literature, we identified four groups of leadership challenges. First, we realised traditional leadership styles are ineffective in IR 4.0, as leaders must embrace transformational, people-orientated, charismatic leadership styles. Future leaders should encourage innovative concepts and concentrate on making their organisations more proficient than their competitors (Balog, K., 2020; Marnewick et al., 2020; Amin et al., 2021; Aminah. S & Saksono. H., 2021; da Silva et al., 2021; Jayashree et al., 2022; Coopasamy. S & Botha. A., 2022; Long et al., 2022). Second, developing soft skills such as English language development, communication, personality development, critical thinking, problem-solving, entrepreneurship, and team-building is essential for success (Satpathy et al., 2020; Subramaniam et al., 2021). Third, in an IR 4.0 context, future leaders must think strategically and creatively and have emotional and social intelligence competencies. Finally, it is critical to create an environment that may stimulate employees and improve the quality of human resources and performance (Kiraz et al., 2020; Rusly et al., 2021; Soomro et al., 2021; Wilson et al., 2021; Hermawan et al., 2020).

This literature review was limited to "Web of Science" and "Scopus" databases and publications from 2020 to 2022 and based on keywords only "Industrial Revolution 4.0" and "Leadership". Future analysis can identify other leadership challenges and solutions by expanding databases, publication years, and keywords.

REFERENCES

1. Amin, S., Mukminin, A., Setiawati, R., & Fitriaty, F. (2021). Empowering leadership and human resources through stimulating innovative behaviors in higher education [Article]. *ZBORNIK RADOVA EKONOMSKOG FAKULTETA U RIJECI-PROCEEDINGS OF RIJEKA FACULTY OF ECONOMICS*, 39(2), 381-399. <https://doi.org/10.18045/zbefri.2021.2.381>
2. Aminah, S., & Saksono, H. (2021). Digital Transformation of the Government: A Case Study in Indonesia [Article]. *JURNAL KOMUNIKASI-MALAYSIAN JOURNAL OF COMMUNICATION*, 37(2), 272-288. <https://doi.org/10.17576/JKMJC-2021-3702-17>
3. Balog, K. (2020). The concept and competitiveness of agile organisation in the fourth industrial revolution's drift [Article]. *STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT*, 25(3), 14-27. <https://doi.org/10.5937/StraMan2003014B>
4. Bartscht, J., (2015). Why systems must explore the unknown to survive in VUCA environments. [online] Semanticscholar.org. Available at: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Why-systems-must-explore-the-unknown-to-survive-in-Bartscht/f209de6c81292f2f86baed4a3a2f1fd59f60e7fb>
5. Bawany, S. (2017). The Future Of Leadership In The Fourth Industrial Revolution. *HR.COM* (12-03-2017).
6. Bennet, N. and Lemonie, G., (2014). What a difference a word makes: Understanding threats to performance in a VUCA world. [online] *RESEARCHGATE*.

8. Coopasamy, S., & Botha, A. P. (2022). LEADERSHIP 4.0: LEADERSHIP CHANGES REQUIRED IN THE SOUTH AFRICAN PETROLEUM INDUSTRY TO SUPPORT THE FOURTH INDUSTRIAL REVOLUTION [Article]. *SOUTH AFRICAN JOURNAL OF INDUSTRIAL ENGINEERING*, 33(2), 96-110. <https://doi.org/10.7166/33-2-2681>
9. da Silva, V., Firmino, T. T., & Amorim, A. F. A. (2021). The perception of managers about the skills required in the context of industry 4.0 [Article]. *REVISTA TECNOLOGIA ESOCIEDADE*, 17(49), 118-132. <https://doi.org/10.3895/rts.v17n49.13631>
10. Frey, C. B., & Osborne, M. (2013). The future of employment.
11. Hermawan, H., Thamrin, H. M., & Susilo, P. (2020). Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Performance: The Role of Employee Engagement [Article]. *JOURNAL OF ASIAN FINANCE ECONOMICS AND BUSINESS*, 7(12), 1089-1097. <https://doi.org/10.13106/jafeb.2020.vol7.no12.1089>
13. Jayashree, S., Reza, M. N. H., Malarvizhi, C. A. N., Gunasekaran, A., & Rauf, M. A. (2022). Testing an adoption model for Industry 4.0 and sustainability: A Malaysian scenario [Article]. *SUSTAINABLE PRODUCTION AND CONSUMPTION*, 31, 313-330. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2022.02.015>
14. Kiraz, A., Canpolat, O., Ozkurt, C., Taskin, H., & Sarp, E. (2020). Examination of the criteria affecting Industry 4.0 with structural equation model and a pilot study [Article]. *JOURNAL OF THE FACULTY OF ENGINEERING AND ARCHITECTURE OF GAZI UNIVERSITY*, 35(4), 2183-2196. <https://doi.org/10.17341/gazimmfd.558947>
15. Long, N. D. B., Ooi, P. T., Le, T. V., Thiet, L. T., Van Ai, T., An, L. Q., Hudson, A., Tan, K. S., & Van, N. T. L. (2022). Leading in the Age of the Fourth Industrial Revolution - A Perspective from Vietnam [Article]. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF TECHNOLOGY*, 13(5), 949-957. <https://doi.org/10.14716/ijtech.v13i5.5839>
16. Marnewick, A. L., & Marnewick, C. (2020). The Ability of Project Managers to Implement Industry 4.0-Related Projects [Article]. *IEEE ACCESS*, 8, 314-324. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2961678>
17. Martos-Vila, M., & Shi, Z. (2022). Bankruptcy Filings During and After the COVID-19 Recession. https://www.americanbar.org/groups/business_law/publications/blt/2022/03/bankruptcy-filings-during-and-after-the-covid-19-recession/
18. Nangia, M. and Mohsin, F., (2020). *Identifying VUCA factors in a pandemic era a framework focused on the Indian IT industry*. [online] Semantic scholar.org. Available at: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/IDENTIFYING-VUCA-FACTORS-IN-A-PANDEMIC-ERA-A-ON-IT-Nangia-Mohsin/a10c99e55398d242e785fbbd318f1084c7ddc96d>
19. Puhovichová, D., & Jankelová, N. (2021). Leadership in Conditions of Industry 4.0. In *SHS Web of Conferences (Vol. 115, p. 03013)*. EDP Sciences.
20. Raghuramatruni, R. and Kosuri, S., (2017). The Straits of Success in a VUCA World. [online] Iosrjournals.org. Available at: <http://www.iosrjournals.org/iosr-jbm/papers/Conf.17016-2017/Volume%201/3.%2016-22.pdf>
21. Rusly, F. H., Talib, Y. Y. A., Hussin, M. R. A., & Mutalib, H. A. (2021). MODELLING THE INTERNAL FORCES OF SMEs DIGITAL ADAPTATION STRATEGY TOWARDS

- INDUSTRY REVOLUTION 4.0 [Article]. *POLISH JOURNAL OF MANAGEMENT STUDIES*, 24(1), 306-321. <https://doi.org/10.17512/pjms.2021.24.1.18>
22. Satpathy, S., Dash, K. K., & Mohapatra, M. (2020). A Study on the New Design Thinking for Industrial Revolution 4.0, Requirements and Graduate Readiness [Article]. *RUPKATHA JOURNAL ON INTERDISCIPLINARY STUDIES IN HUMANITIES*, 12(4). <https://doi.org/10.21659/rupkatha.v12n4.09>
23. Soomro, M. A., Hizam-Hanafiah, M., Abdullah, N. L., Ali, M. H., & Jusoh, M. S. (2021). Embracing Industry 4.0: Empirical Insights from Malaysia [Article]. *INFORMATICS-BASEL*, 8(2), Article 30. <https://doi.org/10.3390/informatics8020030>
24. Subramaniam, M., Noordin, M. K., & Nor, H. M. (2021). Eight Discipline-Problem Based Learning in Industrial Training Program to Develop Future Proof Skills Among Graduate Engineers [Article]. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ONLINE AND BIOMEDICAL ENGINEERING*, 17(12), 38-51. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijoe.v17i12.25481>
25. Schwab, K. (2016). The fourth industrial revolution: What it means, how to respond. *WORLD ECONOMIC FORUM*.
26. Wilson, J. C. M., Kandege, P., Edjoukou, A. J. R., & Teklu, M. T. (2021). Unpacking smart education's soft smartness variables: Leadership and human resources capacities as key participatory actors [Article]. *EDUCATION AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES*, 26(5), 6267-6298. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-021-10599-9>